

EFFECTIVENESS OF USING DIDACTIC GAME TECHNOLOGIES IN MOTHER LANGUAGE AND READING LITERACY LESSONS OF PRIMARY CLASSES

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Abstract. *This article focuses on the methods and importance of engaging students in both the theoretical and practical part of the lesson by means of didactic games to ensure that the native language and reading literacy lessons organized in primary grades are rich in content.*

Keywords: *game, game technologies, didactic games, modern education, innovative environment, elementary school, student, creativity, monotonous activity of mastering.*

The main task of the public education of our republic is to raise healthy, capable people who have matured in all respects and are loyal to their country and people and bring them to adulthood. Realization of this great goal requires all employees and teachers belonging to the public education system to have a creative approach to their work, to come up with various methodological methods to achieve high efficiency in every work, and to apply it to school life. Students studying in schools today are somewhat educated people who enjoy a number of achievements made by the progress of science and technology. Providing knowledge to the student, enriching the content of each lesson, requires incorporating interesting activities into the lesson process. According to psychologists, students retain the knowledge they have acquired through various mental experiences and independently performed work for a long time, compared to the information acquired through the teacher's simple explanation. Because the student performs independent exercises and imagines a lot of educational materials based on the knowledge he has already acquired. And based on these, he compares similar events. He makes an independent judgment about them.

Currently, the school needs to organize its activities in such a way as to ensure the development of individual abilities of each student and a creative attitude to life, the introduction of various innovative educational programs, the implementation of the principle of humanism to students, etc. In other words, the school is very interested in knowing the characteristics of the mental development of each student, in the conscious choice of educational technologies.

The level of education and upbringing in the school is largely determined by the degree to which the pedagogical process is oriented to the psychology of the student's age and individual development. It includes psychological-pedagogical study of schoolchildren during the entire period of study in order to determine the possibilities of individual development, creative abilities of each student, to strengthen his positive activity, to reveal the uniqueness of his personality, to provide timely help in case of lagging behind in studies or unsatisfactory behavior. This is especially important in the lower grades of the school, when the purposeful learning of a person is just beginning, when learning becomes a leading activity, when the student's mental characteristics and qualities, first of all, cognitive processes and attitude towards himself as a subject of knowledge (cognitive motives, self-esteem, ability to cooperate, etc.) are formed in his bosom.

Play, as a phenomenal human phenomenon, is considered in detail in fields of knowledge such as psychology and philosophy. In the pedagogy and teaching method, more attention is paid to the games of preschool and junior school children. This is because teachers see play as an important learning method for preschool and elementary school-aged children. A number of special studies on play activities of preschool children were carried out by well-known teachers of their time.

The study of game activity was not only interesting in the field of preschool education, many famous psychologists, including E. Erikson, L. Vygotsky, P. Galperin, Ya. Kolomensky, K. Gross, and others were engaged in it. According to them, the game plays an important role in the development of a child's personality. In addition to these scientists, the aspects of game activity in the general education school also attracted the attention of scholars. Russian scientists S. V. Harutyunyan, O. S. Gazman, V. M. Grigoryev, O. A. Dyachkova, F. I. Fradkina, G. P. Shchedrovitsky and others are considered scientists who have carried out a number of scientific studies in this regard.

Today, the need to expand methodological potential, especially in active forms of education, is clearly visible in modern schools with an increasingly developing innovative environment and modern education. Therefore, it is possible to include game technologies in such forms of active learning, which are sufficiently covered in the methods of mother tongue and reading literacy classes applied to the primary education processes of the Republic of Uzbekistan today.

Game technologies are one of the unique forms of education, which allows to make not only the creative and research work of students, but also the daily steps in learning literary reading interesting and exciting. The game makes the monotonous activity of memorizing, repeating, consolidating or mastering information more interesting, emotional and fun. Another positive aspect of the game is that it helps to use knowledge in a new situation, so the material learned by the students undergoes a specific practice, it adds variety and interest to the educational process.

The relevance of the game is currently increasing due to the fact that the modern student studying in a modern school is saturated with information. In the whole world, especially in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the topic-information environment is expanding to an incomparable level. Recently, television, video, radio, and computer networks have been "bombarding" students with a lot of information. The urgent task of the school is to develop self-assessment and selection of received information. One of the forms of education that forms such skills are didactic games that help practical use of knowledge acquired in and outside of the classroom.

The game is very important in the life of a developing person. According to psychologists, in the game, the child builds the first models of the world around him, develops his abilities and character, and also learns the rules of communication between people. Play is the practice of children's life, so it reflects what the child already knows, and during play, this knowledge is modified and improved through speech. Active activity of imagination takes place in the game, as a result of which existing knowledge is combined, real ideas are combined with fiction and fantasy. The game not only helps to form communicative qualities necessary for communicating with peers, but also develops resourcefulness, initiative, and ingenuity during the game. Games create vivid emotional experiences and play a stimulating role that has a positive effect on moral education. A child who does not play is, to one degree or another, a child with developmental problems, often this problem is social adjustment.

At the same time, the game technology type of pedagogical technology was widely used in the course of the lesson. Nowadays, a modern teacher should not be an actor, but a "director" in the course of the lesson. He should organize his students to look at science creatively, form in them inquisitiveness, ingenuity and quick work characteristics, as well as organize a lesson using modern pedagogical technologies. For this, it is necessary for the teacher to know new educational methods and methods, to use them effectively in the course of the lesson. Based on this, it can be said that 2023 is not called "Year of attention to people and quality education" for nothing.

Why is it necessary to use modern pedagogical technologies in the course of the lesson? It is not inappropriate to put the urgent question in the center. Modern pedagogical technologies imply the goal of achieving high results in a short time without spending too much mental and physical effort. Among them, didactic games or game technologies, which are one of the modern pedagogical technologies, means a method that activates students and encourages them to think independently, where the learner is at the center of the educational process.

Game technologies are a component of pedagogical technologies. Game technologies can be used as an effective means of activating the learning process in mother tongue and reading literacy classes. The word "game" itself is not a strictly scientific concept, in methodology, this type of work is defined in different ways.

Two main types of games are often distinguished: educational or didactic and business. A business game is an imitation of real activity in artificially created conditions, as a result of which the development of creative abilities, mutual support and mutual education, increasing the quality of knowledge with their complex application. Thus, its function is to learn, and therefore, a business game can also be considered educational.

In conclusion, it can be said that currently game technologies are one of the unique forms of education that not only make students' work interesting and exciting at the creative and research level, but also allow them to learn the mother tongue and reading literacy and other subjects. The game helps to memorize and assimilate information, including the monotonous activity of repetition, as mentioned above, to give an emotional color. Another positive aspect of the game is the application of acquired knowledge in a new situation. Thus, mastering new material occurs through practice and arouses interest in the learning process.

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